

The Art of Science

Developed by: Acabo Games

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Keywords

Biology, Chemistry, Competition, Cooperation, Mathematics, Physics, Science, Technology

Figure 1. Photograph of *The Art of Science* game board and components. © Acabo Games.

Introduction

The Art of Science (see Figure 1) is a trivia game for the nerdy and knowledgeable, with categories of Physics, Biology, Technology, Mathematics, Chemistry, and Other Science, all aimed at the undergraduate or higher levels. It has an interesting point system as well, but the real potency comes from the challenge and diversity of the questions.

This game should appeal to undergraduate science students or instructors looking to see how well-rounded students are.

It can be essential to recognize what students know and how broadly their knowledge extends. *The Art of Science* can provide such insights.

The game works like a Trivial Pursuit-style game, with players on teams taking turns asking and answering questions from a variety of categories. There is a scoring system that allows players to take fewer questions from categories that they find challenging and incorporate them into their win condition. This introduces a tactical component to the gameplay as well.

The game was developed by Acabo Games and released by TerrorBull Games in 2010.

Facts

Release date:	2010
Developer:	Acabo Games
Game type:	Analog
Number of players:	2–6
Format:	Synchronous
Time frame:	30 minutes
Languages:	English, Swedish
Environment:	Tabletop
Material:	No additional material required.
Price:	£29.95

Resonance & Criticism

The Art of Science has largely gone unrecognized, possibly because of the nature of the game (science and math) and the level of difficulty.

The Art of Science has not received awards or ratings of any prominence.

The most prominent point of criticism is the limited number of players with whom one can play this game, given the high level of required knowledge to play adequately. The questions are tricky and span a diverse range of topics with depth.

Game Principle & Process

The Art of Science is a high-level, challenging trivia game with an interesting scoring and dueling mechanic. Players can play individually or in teams (recommended).

The objective is to answer a predetermined number of questions correctly from categories that player choose. One can define their win condition based on a certain number of correct answers in each category. Duels and challenges can amplify this effect.

There is a clear point system for tracking successes and misses that is only somewhat novel. There is limited social interaction in the game, unless you are playing as a team.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

The Art of Science is a trivia game that draws on knowledge from multiple strands of science and mathematics at the undergraduate or graduate level. The mechanics support answering questions correctly while also allowing individual strengths to be utilized and incorporated.

There is no requirement for a teacher to be interactive during gameplay, apart from rule clarifications.

Effectiveness

No empirical evidence has been found to date on the effectiveness or learning impacts of The Art of Science.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

There are no issues with this game, aside from the two available languages and the difficulty level of the questions.

Reviewer(s): Hannes Hamester, Johannes Katsarov

Sources

TerrorBull Games. (n.d.). The art of science [Game information page]. *TerrorBull Games*.
https://www.terrorbullgames.com/games/the_art_of_science_game.php